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ECCE
EUROPEAN CYBERSECURITY
COMPETENCE CENTRE

DIGITAL-ECCE-2022-CYBER-03-UPTAKE-CYBERSOLUTIONS

Grant Agreement number: 101128013

CYBER INSURANCE APPLICATION GUIDE

A BRIEF ANALYSIS FOR THE RATIONALE OF THE MAIN REQUESTED INFORMATION

Release date	23/04/2025
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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Basic Company Information	4
3. Ownership Structure	5
4. Primary contact details	5
5. Primary Industry Sector	5
6. Company Information regarding IT security	6
7. Coverage Components Required	7
8. Types and Number of records	7
9. Applicability / Types of Assets that Exist within Organisation	8
10. Cyber Security Controls	9
11. Control Effectiveness – Denial of Service	10
12. Control Effectiveness – Server/Application	10
13. Claims History	11
14. Conclusion	12
15. References	12

1. **Executive Summary**

Cyber threats continue to evolve in both complexity and impact, affecting organizations of all sizes and sectors. To effectively underwrite cyber risk, insurers require a comprehensive understanding of the applicants' business structure, data handling practices, security controls, historical incidents, and preparedness for potential cyber events.

The information requested in the Cyber Insurance Application form is essential for insurers to accurately assess the applicant's cyber risk exposure, determine the appropriate scope of coverage and ensure the policy is tailored to the specific operational, technical, and regulatory context of an organization.

Each section of the application form is designed to capture relevant and actionable information that supports a thorough risk assessment and promotes transparency between the insured and the insurer. The ultimate goal is to clarify the importance of each data point, ensure understanding for the applicant, and demonstrate how this information contributes to fair and accurate underwriting decisions.

This document provides a justification analysis, explaining the rationale behind each section of the Cyber Insurance Application Form.

2. **Basic Company Information**

- Company Name:
- Primary Address (Address, County, Postcode, Country):
- Date Established:
- Website Address:
- Last Complete Financial Year Gross Revenue:
- Last Complete Financial Year Net Profit:
- Current Financial Year Estimated Revenue:
- Current Financial Year Net Profit:
- Number of Employees:

The information requested in the "Basic Company Information section" is essential for insurers to accurately assess the risk profile, coverage needs and premium pricing for a cyber insurance policy. The company name provides legal identification for underwriting and claims processing, while the primary address helps determine geographic risk factors, applicable regulations, and jurisdiction. The date, the company was established, reflects its operational history and stability, which may influence perceived risk.

A website address offers insight into the nature of the business, its public presence, and potential exposures, especially for businesses with digital operations. Financial details such as gross revenue and net profit from the last financial year, along with current year estimates, indicate the size, financial health, and growth trajectory of the business—critical data for determining appropriate coverage limits and calculating risk exposure.

Lastly, the number of employees is crucial for evaluating risks related to staff number. Collectively, this information enables insurers to provide accurate, customized coverage that aligns with the company's risk profile and operational realities.

3. Ownership Structure

- Publicly Traded
- Privately Held
- Subsidiary of Publicly Traded/Private Held Company (provide details below)
- Other (Government, Local Authority, non-profit, association, etc.; provide details below)

The ownership structure of a company plays a key role in a cyber insurance application, as it helps the insurer understand, who is ultimately responsible for managing cyber risks and how the business is organized. For example, a publicly traded company may have stricter regulatory and cybersecurity compliance requirements, whereas a privately held company may have different internal controls and risk exposure.

If the business is a subsidiary, its cyber risk may be influenced by the parent company's systems, policies, and history of cyber incidents. Understanding the parent company enables the insurer to determine whether any past claims or breaches could impact the application. For government bodies, non-profits, or associations different legal and operational risks may apply, such as specific data handling responsibilities or public accountability. Overall, this information helps the insurer accurately assess the risk level, determine coverage needs and price the policy correctly.

4. Primary contact details

- Contact Name:
- Position:
- Email Address:
- Telephone Number:

The primary contact is the individual responsible for communicating with the insurer, during the application process, policy setup and in the event of a cyber incident. This person should have a solid understanding of the company's operations and cybersecurity practices. Providing accurate contact details ensures the insurer can quickly reach the right person—particularly crucial during a cyber emergency, where a rapid response can minimize damage and reduce claim costs.

5. Primary Industry Sector

- Accommodation and Food Services
- Agriculture, Forestry, Fishing, and Hunting
- Arts, Entertainment, and Recreation
- Construction
- Education
- Finance and Insurance
- Healthcare and Social Assistance
- Information, Software, and Technology
- Management of Companies and Enterprises
- Manufacturing

- Mining
- Other Services (except Public Administration)
- Professional, Scientific, and Technical Services
- Public Administration
- Real Estate Rental and Leasing
- Retail Trade
- Shipping and Marine
- Transportation & Warehousing
- Utilities
- Wholesale Trade
- Waste Management and Remediation Services, and Administration and Support
- Other - Not Listed

Identifying a company's primary industry sector is a critical component of a cyber insurance application, as it enables the insurer to accurately assess the organization's cyber risk profile accurately. Each sector is exposed to different types and levels of cyber threats. For instance, industries such as finance, healthcare, and information technology often manage large volumes of sensitive data, making them frequent targets for cyberattacks. These sectors typically require more robust cybersecurity measures and comprehensive insurance coverage.

In contrast, sectors like construction, agriculture, or retail may have lower digital exposure but can still be affected by risks such as phishing, ransomware, or operational disruptions. Understanding the industry classification allows insurers to evaluate the nature of data handled, the regulatory obligations applicable to the organization, and the potential impact of a cyber incident within that specific field.

By identifying the primary industry sector, insurers can tailor coverage appropriately and ensure accurate risk assessment and pricing. This step is essential for providing effective and relevant protection to the insured organization.

6. Company Information regarding IT security

Approximate operational expenditure on IT security in the last financial year (including salaries, annual licenses, consultancy costs, etc.):

- Anticipated spending versus last year:
- IT infrastructure primarily operated and managed in-house or outsourced?:
- If it is outsourced, who do you outsource it to?:
- Number of full-time employees in IT department:
- Number of employees dedicated to a role in IT security:

This section provides the insurer with insight into the organization's investment in cybersecurity and its internal capabilities. The operational expenditure on IT security—including staffing, tools, and consultancy—reflects the priority placed on protecting digital assets and managing cyber risk. Comparing anticipated spending to the previous year's may reveal, whether the company is proactively strengthening its defenses or reducing investment, which can affect its risk exposure.

Whether the IT infrastructure is managed in-house or outsourced is also a key consideration. In-house teams may provide greater control, while outsourcing introduces third-party risk. Understanding who manages outsourced IT services, allows the insurer to evaluate the reliability and security posture of the vendors involved.

The size of the IT department and the number of employees dedicated to IT security helps to measure the company's capacity to detect, respond to and mitigate cyber threats. Together, these details help the insurer assess the company's cyber readiness, resilience, and overall risk profile, ensuring that the coverage offered is both suitable and fairly priced.

7. Coverage Components Required

- Security, Cyber and Privacy Liability
- Network Interruption
- Cyber Incident Response
- Electronic Data
- System Damage & Business Interruption
- Ransomware / Cyber Extortion
- Cyber Crime

Identifying the required cyber coverage components, allows the insurer to tailor a policy that aligns with the organization's specific operational needs and digital risks. Each component represents a distinct type of exposure that, if not covered, could result in critical financial loss.

Security, Cyber and Privacy Liability covers legal and financial consequences arising from data breach or unauthorized access to confidential information.

Network Interruption protects against income loss and operational disruptions due to network failures or cyber incidents.

Cyber Incident Response ensures that expert support is immediately available following a cyberattack, assisting in containing and mitigating the damage.

Cyber Extortion and Ransomware coverage are crucial in an environment, where attacks demanding payment to restore data or systems are increasingly common.

System Damage & Business Interruption provide protection for repair costs and lost revenue, when critical systems are compromised by an attack. Electronic Data coverage addresses the loss, corruption, or unauthorized access to critical data assets.

Cyber Crime extends coverage to threats such as social engineering, phishing, or financial fraud conducted through digital means.

The aforementioned components selection ensures that its cyber insurance policy is both comprehensive and aligned with the organization risk landscape, enabling faster recovery and minimizing financial impact in the event of a cyber incident.

8. Types and Number of records that the Applicant collects, processes, stores, or are transferred within the Applicant's environment, including records collected, processed, or stored by others for the Applicant.

- PII (Personally Identifiable Information including employee information):
- PCI (Payment Card Information):
- HI (Health Information):
- Government Classified (sensitive or secret government information):

Understanding the type and volume of sensitive data handled by the applicant is essential for assessing cyber risk exposure. Each data category carries unique legal, regulatory, and financial consequences if compromised.

PII includes names, addresses, ID numbers, or employee details and is protected by privacy laws like GDPR. Breach can lead to lawsuits, liability claims and regulatory fines.

PCI refers to credit and debit card data, which falls under the PCI DSS compliance framework. These records are frequent targets for cybercriminals.

HI, such as patient data, is subject to strict regulations like HIPAA and a breach can result in severe reputational and legal consequences.

Government Classified Information involves sensitive national or local government data, requiring heightened security protocols and potentially carrying national security implications.

By disclosing the type and quantity of records handled internally or by third parties, the applicant enables the insurer to estimate the potential impact of a cyber incident, determine appropriate coverage limits, and assess regulatory exposure. This ensures that the policy is accurately priced and tailored to the organization's risk profile.

9. Applicability / Types of Assets that Exist within Organisation

- Asset description Value in €
- Web Applications
- Point of Sale (PoS) Systems
- End User Systems (laptops, desktops, mobile devices, tablets, etc.)
- Terminals (ATMs, kiosks, payment terminals, etc.)
- Removable Media (USB storage devices, offline data repositories, etc.)
- Industrial Control Systems (ICS), Supervisory Control & Data Acquisition (SCADA), or Operational Technology (OT)
- Healthcare Devices (including life support systems, insulin drips, health monitoring systems, etc.)
- Onboard Systems (operating systems which control vehicles, such as trains, cars, or airplanes)
- Critical Internet of Thing (IoT) Devices (door locks/actuators, smoke detectors, etc.)

Non-Critical Internet of Thing (IoT) Devices

The identification and valuation of technology assets within an organization is essential in evaluating the cyber exposure and insurable risk. Different types of assets carry varying levels of criticality and vulnerability to cyber threats.

Web applications and PoS systems are common targets for external attacks, including data breach and malware intrusion.

End-user systems such as laptops and mobile devices are often entry points for phishing and ransomware attacks, due to user interaction and mobility.

Terminals and removable media pose unique risks related to physical access and unmonitored data transfers.

Industrial control systems (ICS), SCADA, and OT are often critical to operational continuity, particularly in manufacturing, energy, and utilities, and may lack modern cybersecurity protections.

Healthcare devices present both patient safety and data privacy risks.

Onboard systems and IoT devices (critical and non-critical) increase the attack surface and require specific security considerations due to constant connectivity and operational dependence.

Providing this information allows the insurer to understand the organization's technical landscape, assess business continuity risks and estimate potential financial loss, in the event of a cyber incident. It also ensures that policy coverage is properly aligned with the real-world value and importance of the assets.

10. Cyber Security Controls

Select from the below those related to controls that you currently have implemented within your IT infrastructure (including where provided by a third party).

- Advanced Endpoint Protection
- Application Whitelisting
- Asset Inventory
- Custom Threat Intelligence
- Database Encryption
- Data Loss Prevention (DLP)
- DDoS Mitigation
- DMARC
- DNS Filtering
- Employee Awareness Training
- Incident Response Plan
- Intrusion Detection System
- Mobile Device Encryption
- Penetration Tests
- Perimeter Firewalls
- Security Info & Event Management
- Two-factor Authentication
- Vulnerability Scans
- Web Application Firewall
- Web Content Filtering

The list of implemented cybersecurity controls provides insurers with a clear view of the organization's proactive security posture. These controls are essential for preventing, detecting and responding to cyber threats and directly influence both the likelihood and potential severity of a cyber incident.

Controls such as firewalls, endpoint protection, intrusion detection systems, and SIEM solutions form the foundation of perimeter and internal defense. Additional measures like data encryption, DLP, and application whitelisting reduce the risk of data breach and unauthorized access.

Employee training and incident response plans are key to ensure preparedness and reduce human error, which is one of the most common causes of breach. Advanced measures like penetration testing, custom threat intelligence and DMARC support the organization's ability to anticipate, detect and mitigate targeted threats.

By identifying which controls are in place—whether managed internally or outsourced—insurers can assess the organization's maturity in cyber risk management, which affects coverage terms, eligibility, and pricing. Strong security controls may also lead to lower premiums or improved policy conditions.

11. Control Effectiveness – Denial of Service

Does The Applicant... (YES or NO type of answers)

- *- and the Applicant's cloud provider(s) if any - have a DDoS mitigation service?
- *have its own DoS response plans?
- *conduct at least annual training to ensure the operations teams know how to engage and leverage the DDoS mitigation service?
- *conduct mock DoS attacks to ensure that the operations teams perform successfully, tune the monitoring solution, and/or test the DDoS mitigation service?

These questions evaluate the organization's preparedness to handle Denial of Service (DoS) and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, which are among the most common and disruptive forms of cyber threats.

A DDoS mitigation service, whether provided in-house or by a cloud vendor, is essential to filter and block malicious traffic before it impacts services. The existence of a formal DoS response plan ensures the organization has defined steps for quickly containing and recovering from an attack.

Regular training for operations teams is critical to ensure personnel know how to activate mitigation tools and follow procedures under pressure. Conducting mock DoS attack simulations reflects a mature and proactive approach, allowing the organization to validate its readiness, improve response times, and fine-tune both manual and automated defenses.

By evaluating these controls, insurers can measure the applicant's resilience to service disruption attacks, which directly affect business continuity and claim risk. Strong DoS-related preparedness can influence underwriting decisions and lead to better coverage conditions.

12. Control Effectiveness – Server/Application

Does The Applicant... (YES or NO type of answers)

- *establish, implement, and manage a secure configuration for each server, including keeping software up to date, patching vulnerabilities, disabling unnecessary services, and hardening configurations after each monthly risk assessment?

- *have a host-based DLP solution that can be used to enforce ACL's even when data is copied off the server?
- *segment critical servers from the user, point of sale, printer, wireless, terminal, and/or partners' networks?
- *encrypt all critical server communications?
- *encrypt all sensitive information at rest within critical servers?
- *use least privilege permissions (or rights) to limit access to critical servers and the data within the critical servers?
- *require the use of multifactor authentication for all critical server or critical application administrators?
- *require the use of multifactor authentication for all domain user accounts and/or critical application accounts?
- *both perform quarterly internal risk assessments for the external server environment(s) and remediate all high severity vulnerabilities between assessment periods?
- *both perform quarterly internal risk assessments of the internal server environment(s) and remediate all high severity vulnerabilities between assessment periods?
- *perform quarterly critical server /application penetration tests or red team exercises to discover critical server/application weaknesses, and test the Applicant's server/application incident response?
- Does the Applicant implement and maintain any of the following malware defenses on servers? (select all that apply)
 - Antivirus
 - Anti-spyware
 - Host-based or network-based intrusion prevention systems

This section evaluates the depth of security controls and hardening practices applied to an organization's critical servers and applications, which are often targeted in cyberattacks.

Proper server configuration management, vulnerability patching and access control are foundational in reducing attack surfaces. To protect sensitive data, encryption is used to ensure confidentiality both at rest and in transit. These measures are reinforced by network segmentation and the principle of least privilege, which limit lateral movement and restrict unauthorized access during a breach.

Requiring multifactor authentication (MFA) for administrative and user access adds a strong layer of identity security. Quarterly risk assessments, when combined with timely remediation, reflect a proactive and ongoing commitment to server security. Regular penetration testing and red teaming enhance this posture by uncovering hidden weaknesses and evaluate real-world response readiness.

In terms of malware defense, tools like antivirus, anti-spyware and host-based or network-based intrusion prevention systems, remain critical. These tools are essential for detecting and preventing known threats on servers. Together, these controls offer a comprehensive view of the organization's ability to protect its most sensitive systems. By evaluating the presence and maturity of these defences, insurers can more accurately cyber readiness determine risk exposure and make informed underwriting decisions, ultimately influencing eligibility, policy conditions and pricing.

13. Claims History

- During the past 5 years, has the Applicant experienced any occurrences, Claims or Losses related to a failure of security of the Applicant's computer systems or has anyone sued or made a Claim against the Applicant

with regard to invasion or interference with rights of privacy, wrongful disclosure of Confidential Information or does the Applicant have knowledge of a situation or circumstance which might otherwise result in a Claim against the Applicant with regard to issues related to the Insurance Sought?

- Yes
- No
- Not Applicable

Disclosure of claims history allows the insurer to evaluate the applicant's prior exposure to cyber incidents, data privacy breach, or legal actions related to information security. A pattern of incidents may indicate existing vulnerabilities, recurring issues, or gaps in cybersecurity practices that require attention.

In addition, information about any pending or likely claims enables the insurer to assess existing risks that could materialize during the policy period. Accurate claims history also plays a crucial role in determining policy terms, coverage limits, exclusions, and premium pricing. Incomplete or inaccurate responses may result in denied claims or rescission of the policy in the future.

Ultimately, this section ensures that underwriting decisions are based on a comprehensive understanding of the organization's risk background and preparedness.

14. Conclusion

The information outlined above is indicative. The Cyber Insurance Application's wording and the size of requested information may differ depending on factors such as the company size, the industry and the complexity of the risk under consideration. Additionally, differences in wording and structure of the application may exist between different insurance companies as well.

It is also crucial to recognize that the cyber threat landscape is continuously evolving, driven by emerging technologies, regulatory developments, and increasingly sophisticated attack vectors. As a result, both insurers and applicants must remain adaptive and responsive in their approach to evaluating and documenting cyber risk. A well-structured and regularly reviewed application form not only ensures better risk visibility but also fosters more effective interaction between insurers and insured entities. This proactive approach contributes to more resilient organisations and a more robust cyber insurance market.

15. References

The formulation of the presented application form is mainly based on the content of the relevant forms of AIG Insurance Company and CFC Underwriting.